

RAUZY-VEECH RENORMALIZATIONS OF CIRCLE DIFFEOMORPHISMS WITH SEVERAL BREAK POINTS

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Abstract. Let f be an orientation-preserving circle diffeomorphism with irrational rotation number of bounded type and finite number of break points, that is, the derivative f' has discontinuities of first kind at these points. Suppose f' satisfies a certain Zygmund condition which be dependent on parameter $\gamma > 0$ on each continuity intervals. We prove that the Rauzy-Veech renormalisations of f are approximated by Mobius transformations in C^2 -norm if $\gamma \in (1, \infty)$. In particular, we show that if f has zero mean nonlinearity, renormalisation of such maps approximated by piecewise affine interval exchange maps.

Keywords: circle diffeomorphism; break point; renormalisation; interval exchange transformation; Mobius transformation; Rauzy-Veech induction.

Аннотация. Пусть f будет сохраняющим ориентацию диффеоморфизмом окружности с иррациональным числом вращения ограниченного типа и конечным числом точек разрыва, то есть производная имеет разрывы первого рода в этих точках. Предположим, что f' удовлетворяет некоторому условию Зигмунда, которое зависит от параметра $\gamma > 0$ на каждом интервале непрерывности. Мы доказываем, что перенормировки Розы-Вича аппроксимируются преобразованиями Мёбиуса в C^2 -норме, если $\gamma \in (1, \infty)$. В частности, мы показываем, что если имеет нулевую среднюю нелинейность, перенормировка таких отображений аппроксимируется кусочно-аффинными отображениями обмена интервалами.

Ключевые слова: диффеоморфизм окружности, точка разрыва, перенормировка, преобразование обмена интервалами, преобразование Мёбиуса, Индукция Розы-Вича.

Annotatsiya. Faraz qilaylik f yo'nalishini saqlovchi, burish soni irratsional bo'lgan va chekli sondagi sinish tipidagi maxsuslikka ega bo'lgan, yani shu nuqtalarda bir tomonli hosilalar mavjud lekin ular bir biriga teng emas, aylana diffeomorfizmi bo'lsin. Undan tashqari f' parameter $\gamma > 0$ ga bog'liq bo'lgan Zymund shartini qanoatlantirsin. Ushbu ishda biz, agar $\gamma \in (1, \infty)$ bo'lsa Rozi-Vich renormalizatsiyasi C^2 -normada Muyuobus akslantirishlari bilan approksimatsiya qilishini ko'rsatdik. Hususiy holda, agar chiziqsizlini nolga bo'lsa bunday asklantirishlar bo'lakli affin akslantirishlari bilan approksimatsiya qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: aylana diffeomorfizmi; uzilish nuqtasi, renormalizatsiya, intervalli almashinuv transformatsiyasi, Mobius transformatsiyasi, Rauzy-Veech induksiyasi.

Introduction

This work is an extension of our recent result obtained in. The problems on conjugacies and renormalisations of circle diffeomorphisms are the most actual problems in the theory of circle dynamics. Nowadays these problems have been intensively study by many researchers. The origin of the problem of singularity of conjugacy of piecewise linear circle homeomorphisms with two break points goes back to Herman in 1979. Since then the generalisation of Herman's result for the general case, that is homeomorphisms with $n \geq 3$ break points and trivial product jump has been opened. We have solved this problem under a certain condition. Our proof is based on to analyse renormalisations of Sinai and Knaflin (1989), Mackay (1988) and Stark (1988). Poincare

in 1885 noticed that the orbit structure of orientation-preserving diffeomorphism f is determined by some irrational mod 1, called the rotation number of f and denoted by $\rho = \rho(f)$, in the following sense: for any $x \in S^1$ the mapping $f^j(x) \rightarrow j\rho$ is orientation-preserving. Denjoy (1932) proved that if f is the orientation-preserving C^1 -diffeomorphism of the circle with irrational rotation number ρ and $\log f'$ has bounded variation then, the orbit $\{f^j(x)\}_{j \in \mathbb{Z}}$ is dense and the mapping $f^j(x) \rightarrow j\rho \pmod{1}$ can therefore be extended by continuity to a homeomorphism h of S^1 which conjugates f to the linear rotation $f_\rho : x \rightarrow x + \rho \pmod{1}$. The problem of smoothness of the conjugacy of smooth diffeomorphisms has come to be very well understood by authors (Herman 1979; Yoccoz 1984; Khanin & Sinai 1987, 1989; Katznelson & Ornstein 1989). They have shown that if f is C^3 or $C^{2+\alpha}$ and ρ satisfies certain Diophantine condition then the conjugacy will be at least C^1 . A natural generalisation of diffeomorphism of the circle are diffeomorphisms with breaks, those are, circle diffeomorphisms which are smooth everywhere with the exception of finitely many points at which their derivative has discontinuities of the first kind. Circle diffeomorphisms with breaks were introduced by Khanin and Vul (1990; 1991) at the beginning of 90's. They proved that the renormalisations of $C^{2+\alpha}$ diffeomorphisms converge exponentially to a two-dimensional space of the Mobius transformations. Recently Cunha and Smiana (2013) studied Rauzy-Veech renormalisations of $C^{2+\alpha}$ circle diffeomorphisms with several break points. The main idea of this work is to consider piecewise-smooth circle homeomorphisms as generalised interval exchange transformations. They have proved that Rauzy-Veech renormalisations of $C^{2+\alpha}$ generalised interval exchange maps satisfying a certain combinatorial conditions are approximated by Mobius transformations in C^2 -norm. In this work we have generalised their result to a wider class of circle diffeomorphisms the so-called *Zygmund class*. Further, we consider two circle homeomorphisms with the same irrational rotation number of bounded type and finite number of break points. We study these maps as the generalised interval exchange maps. We prove that if two such circle homeomorphisms are not break equivalent then the conjugating map between them is singular. In particular, if one of them is pure rotation then the invariant measure of second one is singular with respect to Lebesgue measure.

Generalised interval exchange maps

Let I be an open bounded interval. A generalised interval exchange map (g.i.e.m) T on I is defined by the following data. Let A be an alphabet with $d \geq 2$ symbols. Consider a partition (mod 0) of I into d open subintervals indexed by $I = \cup I_\alpha$. The map T is defined on $\cup I_\alpha$ and its restriction to each I_α is an orientation preserving homeomorphism onto the $f(I_\alpha)$. Let $r > 1$ be an integer. The g.i.e.m T is of class C^r if the restriction of T to each I_α extends to a C^r -diffeomorphism from the closure of I_α onto of closure of $f(I_\alpha)$. The points $u_1 < \dots < u_{d-1}$ separating the I_α are called the singularities (break points) of T .

Rauzy-Veech Induction

A pair $\pi = (\pi_0, \pi_1)$ of bijections $\pi_\varepsilon : A \rightarrow \{1, \dots, d\}$, $\varepsilon \in \{0, 1\}$ describing the ordering of the subintervals I_α before and after the map is iterated. For each $\varepsilon \in \{0, 1\}$, define $\alpha(\varepsilon) = \pi_\varepsilon^{-1}(d)$. If $|I_{\alpha(0)}| \neq |f(I_{\alpha(1)})|$ we say that f is Rauzy-Veech renormalisable (or simply renormalisable). If $|I_{\alpha(0)}| > |f(I_{\alpha(1)})|$ we say that the letter $\alpha(0)$ is the winner and the letter $\alpha(1)$ is the loser, we say

that f is type 0 renormalisable and we can define a map $R(f)$ as the first return map of f to the interval $I^1 = I \setminus f(I_{\alpha(1)})$. Otherwise $|I_{\alpha(0)}| < |f(I_{\alpha(1)})|$, the letter $\alpha(1)$ is the winner and the letter $\alpha(0)$ is the loser, we say that f is type 1 renormalisable and we can define a map $R(f)$ as the first return map of f to the interval $I^1 = I \setminus f(I_{\alpha(0)})$. We want to see $R(f)$ as a g.i.e.m. To this end we need to associate to this map an A -indexed partition of its domain. We do this in the following way. The subintervals of the A -indexed partition P^1 of I^1 are denoted by I_α^1 . If f has type 0, then $I_\alpha^1 = I_\alpha$ when $\alpha \neq \alpha(0)$ and $I_{\alpha(0)}^1 = I_{\alpha(0)} \setminus f(I_{\alpha(1)})$. If f has type 1, $I_\alpha^1 = I_\alpha$ when $\alpha \neq \alpha(1), \alpha(0)$ and $I_{\alpha(1)}^1 = f^{-1}(f(I_{\alpha(1)}) \setminus I_{\alpha(0)})$, $I_{\alpha(0)}^1 = I_{\alpha(1)} \setminus I_{\alpha(1)}^1$. It is easy to see that both cases (type 0 and 1) we have

$$R(f)(x) = \begin{cases} f^2(x), & \text{if } x \in I_{\alpha(1-\varepsilon)}^1, \\ f(x), & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

And $(R(f), A, P^1)$ is a g.i.e.m, called the Rauzy-Veech renormalisation (or simply renormalisation) of f . A g.i.e.m. is infinitely renormalisable if $R^n(f)$ is well defined, for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$. For every interval of the form $J = [a, b)$ we denote $\partial J = \{a\}$. We say that a g.i.e.m. f has no connection if $f^m(\partial I_\alpha) \neq \partial I_\beta$ for all $m \geq 1$, $\alpha, \beta \in A$ with $\pi_0(\beta) \neq 1$. Let ε_n be the type of the n -th renormalisation, $\alpha_n(\varepsilon_n)$ be the winner and $\alpha_n(1-\varepsilon_n)$ be the loser of the n -th renormalisation. We say that infinitely renormalisable g.i.e.m. f has k -bounded combinatorics (i.e., “rotation number” is bounded type) if for each n and $\beta, \gamma \in A$ there exist $n_1, p \geq 0$ with $|n - n_1| < k$ and $|n - n_1 - p| < k$ such that $\alpha_{n_1}(\varepsilon_{n_1}) = \beta$, $\alpha_{n_1+p}(1-\varepsilon_{n_1+p}) = \gamma$ and $\alpha_{n_1+i}(1-\varepsilon_{n_1+p}) = \alpha_{n_1+i+1}(\varepsilon_{n_1+i})$ for every $0 \leq i < p$. We say that a g.i.e.m. $f: I \rightarrow I$ has genus one if f has at most two discontinuities. Note that every g.i.e.m. with either two or three intervals has genus one. If f is renormalisable and has genus one, it is easy to see that $R(f)$ has genus one. Note that an acceleration of Rauzy-Veech renormalisation is the Mackay-Stark renormalisation and an acceleration of Mackay-Stark renormalisation is the Sinai-Knani renormalisation.

Zygmund Class

To formulate our results we have to define a new class. For this we consider the function $Z^\gamma: [0, 1) \rightarrow (0, +\infty)$ such that $Z^\gamma(0) = 0$ and

$$Z^\gamma(x) = \left(\log \frac{1}{x} \right)^{-\gamma} \quad x \in (0, 1) \text{ and } \gamma > 0.$$

Let $T = [a, b]$ be a finite interval and consider a continuous function $K: T \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. Denote by $\Delta^2 K(x, \tau)$ the second symmetric difference of f on J , i.e.,

$$\Delta^2 K(x, \tau) = K(x + \tau) + K(x - \tau) - 2K(x),$$

where $x \in T$, $\tau \in \left[0, \frac{|T|}{2} \right]$ and $x + \tau, x - \tau \in T$. Now we are ready to define a new class.

Definition 4.1. Let $Z_k^{1+\gamma}$, $k \in \mathbb{N}$ and $\gamma > 0$, be the set of g.i.e.m. $f: I \rightarrow I$ such that

For each $\alpha \in A$ we can extend f to \bar{I}_α as an orientation preserving diffeomorphism;

On each \bar{I}_α , f' satisfies $\left\| \Delta^2 f'(\cdot, \tau) \right\|_{L^\infty(\bar{I}_\alpha)} \leq C\tau Z^\gamma(\tau)$;

The g.i.e.m. f has k -bounded combinatorics;

The map f has genus one and has no connection.

Main Results

We need the following notions. Let H be a non-degenerate interval, let $g : H \rightarrow \square$ be a diffeomorphism and let $J \subset H$ be an interval. We define the Zoom of g in H , denoted by $\Xi_H(g)$ the transformation $\Xi_H(g) = A_1 \circ g \circ A_2$ where A_1 and A_2 are orientation-preserving affine maps, which sends $[0,1]$ into H and $g(H)$ into $[0,1]$ respectively. Let M_N be a Mobius transformation $M_N : [0,1] \rightarrow [0,1]$ such that $M_N(0) = 0$, $M_N(1) = 1$ and

$$M_N(x) = \frac{xN}{1+x(N-1)}.$$

Denote by $q_n^\alpha \in \square$ the first return time of the interval I_α^n to the interval I^n , i.e., $R^n(f)|_{I_\alpha^n} = f^{q_n^\alpha}$ for some $q_n^\alpha \in \square$. Now we define a new quantity as follows:

$$\hat{m}_n^\alpha = \exp\left(-\sum_{i=0}^{q_n^\alpha-1} \frac{f'(d_\alpha^i) - f'(c_\alpha^i)}{2f'(d_\alpha^i)}\right),$$

where c_α^i and d_α^i are the left and right endpoints of $f^i(\bar{I}_\alpha)$, respectively. Recently we have obtained the following result in (Akhadkulov 2024).

Theorem 5.1 (Akhadkulov 2024). *Let $f \in Z_k^{1+\gamma}$, $\gamma \in (0,1]$. Then there exists a constant $C = C(f) > 0$ such that*

$$\left\| \Xi_{I_\alpha^n}(R^n(f)) - M_{\hat{m}_n^\alpha} \right\|_{C^1([0,1])} \leq \frac{C}{n^\gamma}$$

for all $\alpha \in A$.

Note that the class $Z_k^{1+\gamma}$ is “better” when γ increases. More precisely, if $\gamma > 1$ then second derivative of f exists on each continuity intervals of f' . This gives more opportunities to better understand behaviour of $\Xi_{I_\alpha^n}(R^n(f))$. Next, instead of \hat{m}_n^α we define a new quantity as follows:

$$m_n^\alpha = \exp\left(-\sum_{i=0}^{q_n^\alpha-1} \int_{c_\alpha^i}^{d_\alpha^i} \frac{f''(x)}{2f'(x)} dx\right).$$

Note that $\log m_n^\alpha$ is called *nonlinearity* of $R^n(f)$ on I_α^n . Using differentiability of f' easily can be shown that m_n^α is exponential close to the \hat{m}_n^α . Our second main result is the following:

Theorem 5.2. *Let $f \in Z_k^{1+\gamma}$, $\gamma > 1$. Then there exists a constant $C = C(f) > 0$ such that*

$$\left\| \Xi_{I_\alpha^n}(R^n(f)) - M_{m_n^\alpha} \right\|_{C^1([0,1])} \leq \frac{C}{n^\gamma}$$

and

$$\left\| \Xi_{I_\alpha^n}(R^n(f)) - M_{m_n^\alpha} \right\|_{C^0([0,1])} \leq \frac{C}{n^\gamma}$$

for all $\alpha \in A$.

For the nonlinearity of n -th renormalisation of f the following estimation holds:

Theorem 5.3. Let $f \in Z_k^{1+\gamma}$, $\gamma > 1$. Then there exists a constant $C = C(f) > 0$ such that

$$\left| m_n^\alpha - \frac{\sum_{i=0}^{q_n^\alpha-1} |f^i(I_n^\alpha)|}{|I|} \int_0^1 \frac{f''(x)}{f'(x)} dx \right| \leq \frac{C}{n^{\gamma-1}}.$$

In particular, if $\int_0^1 \frac{f''(x)}{f'(x)} dx = 0$ then $|m_n^\alpha| \leq \frac{C}{n^{\gamma-1}}$.

Note that Theorems 5.1, 5.2 and 5.3 generalise the results of Cunha and Smania (2013).

REFERENCES

1. Akhadkulov Habibulla, Approximations for Rauzy-Veech renormalizations of the generalized interval exchange maps. *Acta NUUZ* vol. 2, No. 2.1.1, pp. 16-26, (2024).
2. Cunha K. & Smania D. 2013. Renormalization for piecewise smooth homeomorphisms on the circle. *Ann. I. H. Poincaré – AN* 30: 441-462.
3. Cunha K. & Smania D. 2014. Rigidity for piecewise smooth homeomorphisms on the circle. *Advances in Mathematics* 250: 193-226.
4. Denjoy A. 1932. Sur les courbes définies par les équations différentielles à la surface du tore. *J. Math. Pures Appl.* 11: 333-375.
5. Herman M. 1979. Sur la conjugaison différentiable des difféomorphismes du cercle à des rotations. *Inst. Hautes Etudes Sci. Publ. Math.* 49: 5-234.
6. Hu J. & Sullivan D. 1997. Topological Conjugacy of Circle Diffeomorphisms. *Ergod. Theory Dyn. Sys.* 17(1): 173-186.
7. Katznelson Y. & Ornstein D. 1989. The differentiability of the conjugation of certain diffeomorphisms of the circle. *Ergod.Theor. Dyn. Syst.* 9: 643-680.
8. Katznelson Y. & Ornstein D. 1989. The differentiability of the conjugation of certain diffeomorphisms of the circle. *Ergod.Theor. Dyn. Syst.* 9: 681-690.
9. Khanin K. & Sinai Ya. 1987. A New Proof of M. Herman's Theorem. *Commun. Math. Phys.* 112: 89-101.
10. Khanin K. & Sinai Ya. 1989. Smoothness of conjugacies of diffeomorphisms of the circle with rotations. *Russ. Math. Surv.* 44: 69-99 (translation of *Usp. Mat. Nauk*, 44: 57-82).
11. Khanin K. & Vul E. 1991. Circle homeomorphisms with weak discontinuities. *Amer. Math. Soc*, Providence, 57-98.
12. Khanin K. & Vul E. 1990. Homeomorphisms of the circle with singularities of break type. *Uspekhi Mat. Nauk*, 45 (3), 189-190; English transl. *Russian Math. Surveys* 45(3): 229-230.
13. Mackay R. 1988. A simple proof of Denjoy's theorem. *Math. Proc. Camb. Phil. Soc.* 103: 299-303.
14. Stark J. 1988. Smooth conjugacy and renormalization for diffeomorphisms of the circle. *Nonlinearity* 1: 541-575.
15. Yoccoz J. C. 1984. Conjugaison différentiable des difféomorphismes du cercle dont le nombre de rotation vérifie une condition diophantienne, *Ann. Sci. Ecole Norm. Sup.* 17 (3), 333- 359 .